

Investigating the Effect of the Service Quality Attributes on Diner Satisfaction and Post-dining Behavioral Intention in the Chinese Restaurant Setting

Most. Sharmin Sultana & Niu Xiongying

Abstract

In the setting of a Chinese restaurant in Bangladesh, the current study seeks to investigate the influence of three service quality indicators on diners' satisfaction and the impact of satisfaction on customers' behavioral intention. The author utilized an online survey to obtain primary data from 212 customers who had eating experience in a Chinese restaurant in Bangladesh for the aim of the study. The gathered data was analyzed using SPSS version 22. Reliability analysis, descriptive statistics, correlation, multiple regression analysis, and hypothesis testing were among the statistical methods utilized. The findings show that three aspects of service quality (food, atmosphere, and employee service) have a positive and substantial impact on diners' satisfaction, and that diners' contentment has a strong positive impact on their behavioral intentions. Both conceptually and practically, the research findings are significant. The findings might help restaurant management improve customer happiness and behavior intention (e.g. positive loyalty, WOM, and revisit intention).

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

Customer happiness is commonly assumed to be the result of providing high-quality service in today's highly competitive industry (Han and Ryu, 2007). When customers evaluate service quality based on their experience in the restaurant sector, they often regard cuisine, atmosphere, and personnel services as significant qualities (Chow et al., 2007; Namkung and Jang, 2008; Ryu and Han, 2010). A good balance of these important characteristics in restaurants helps to establish consumer perceptions of great service quality, which leads to higher levels of customer satisfaction and loyalty. In the context of Chinese restaurants in Bangladesh, the current study aims to explore the influence of variables such as food quality, atmosphere, and employee service on customer happiness, as well as the impact of satisfaction on behavioral intention. Service excellence is a nebulous and ephemeral notion. Because of the many structures of the service sector, assessing the quality of services is often considered to be more difficult, as it involves numerous emotional aspects (Fitzsimmons and Fitzsimmons, 2008). As a result, the author's motivation for doing this research is to examine essential aspects of service quality and their relationships with customer satisfaction.

In Bangladesh's service economy, the restaurant business is quite important. Due to an increasing number of new rivals offering differentiated food goods and services, it is comparably competitive with robust rivalry within the service industry. Customers are also growing more serious (Stevens et al., 1995), and their requirements are becoming more diverse. Although Bangladeshi-style Chinese cuisine is offered in restaurants, Chinese food is widely accepted in Bangladesh. Other Asian eateries have also opened, posing a rising threat to Chinese establishments (e.g. Indian, Korean, Vietnam, and Thai restaurants). Furthermore, Bangladeshi restaurant patrons are increasingly concerned about service quality. It is critical to understand the function and relative relevance of the various important variables that will most likely influence pleasure and behavioral intention in this respect. Some questions occur in the researcher's head as a result of the problem statement, such as

RQ-1: What are the major service quality aspects that influence the pleasure of Chinese restaurant patrons?

RQ-2: How does customer satisfaction in a Chinese restaurant influence customer behavior?

In the prior literature, the influence of service quality factors such as cuisine, atmosphere, and personnel service on customer satisfaction and behavioral intention in Chinese restaurant settings was unclear. As a result, the author aims to make it obvious by looking at the impact of service quality qualities on customer satisfaction experimentally. The study has two specific objectives: I to look into the impact of service quality attributes (such as food, atmosphere, and employee service) on diners' satisfaction in Chinese restaurants; and (ii) to look into the impact of diners' satisfaction on their post-dining behavioral intention in Chinese restaurants.

The current research has significant theoretical and practical implications. The author intends to explore how diners' perceptions of restaurant quality affect customer satisfaction, which in turn influences consumer behavioral intention, using customers' dining experiences in Bangladeshi Chinese restaurants. Although the link between service quality characteristics and satisfaction is well understood, it is uncertain in the context of Chinese restaurants. As a result, the author believes that the results of this study will add to the current literature. The findings of this study also assist restaurant managers in understanding the impact of each characteristic on customer happiness and allocating resources to various aspects depending on their contributions to customer satisfaction in order to achieve the maximum level of customer satisfaction possible.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Restaurant Service Quality Attributes (Food, atmospherics, and employee Service)

Perceived service quality is the customer's assessment of the service's overall quality or excellence (Zeithaml, 1988). The subjective calculation that comes from a comparison of expectations and actual performance is the customer's subjective calculation. Customers in the restaurant business analyze not just the quality of the cuisine but also the restaurant's physical surroundings throughout their eating experience. As a result, these service quality qualities have a role in perceived service quality, which is considered as a key driver of customer satisfaction and behavioral intention. Kivela et al. (1999, 2000), for example, presented a complete model for eating satisfaction and repeat business. Customers' happiness with five characteristics of a restaurant influenced their likelihood of returning patronage, according to their research: first and final impressions, service quality, ambiance quality, food quality and feeling comfortable dining there, reservations and parking. Ladhari et al. (2008) looked at the factors that influence dining satisfaction and post-dining behavioral intentions, and found that both positive and negative emotions influenced consumer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction, in turn, has an impact on referrals, loyalty, and readiness to spend more. In certain research, service quality was even found to be more significant than food quality in predicting dining pleasure. For example, Yuksel and Yusel (2002) found that at the aggregate market level, service quality had the greatest impact on eating pleasure, particularly for adventurous or healthy food seekers. Few recent research have shown that cuisine, physical environment, and personnel services should all be considered important elements of the restaurant experience when developing restaurant service quality impressions (Chow et al., 2007; Jang and Namkung, 2009; Namkung and Jang, 2008; Ryu and Han, 2010). In the setting of a full-service restaurant, Chow et al. (2007) studied the connections between service quality, customer satisfaction, and frequency of patronage. They were able to capture three aspects of service quality (i.e. interaction quality, physical quality, outcome quality).

In the setting of mid-to-upper-scale restaurants, Namkung and Jang (2008) performed a study to discover critical quality factors that significantly separate highly satisfied diners from non-very satisfied diners. They measured guests' perceived quality in connection to the restaurant experience using three quality variables (food, atmosphere, and service). Furthermore, Jang and Namkung (2009) expanded on Mehrabian and Russell's (1974) model by include restaurant-specific stimuli and emotional measures. This study employed three elements of restaurant quality: product, atmosphere, and service, to address a lack of thorough evaluation of restaurant service quality. In addition, Ryu and Han (2010) looked at the connections between three quality factors (food, service, and physical environment), pricing, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intention in quick-casual restaurants. Similarly, this study tried to comprehend the impact of three aspects of foodservice quality (food, service, and physical environment) on restaurant customer reaction.

2.2. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is defined as an assessment of a purchase choice made after it has been made (Day, 1984). Customer satisfaction may be described as a customer's overall assessment of his or her experience purchasing and consuming products or services (Cronin & Taylor). Satisfaction is a function of received performance and expectations, to put it another way. The consumer is disappointed when the performance falls short of expectations. The consumer is happy if the performance meets their expectations. Expectations are beliefs (likely or probability) that a product and/or service (having particular traits, features, or characteristics) would generate specific outcomes (benefits or values) based on past affective, cognitive, and behavioral experiences. Expectancy-disconfirmation theory (Oliver, 1981), contrast theory

(Howard and Sheth, 1969), assimilation or cognitive dissonance theory (Anderson, 1973), equity theory (Oliver and Swan, 1989), and value-percept theory (Oliver and Swan, 1989) are just a few of the theories that have been proposed to explain the mechanism of customer satisfaction (Westbrook and Reilly, 1983). The expectation disconfirmation theory is the most commonly recognized among them. Customers' satisfaction assessments, according to this idea, are the outcome of comparisons between consumer expectations and perceived performance. The expectation is positively disproved and the consumer is satisfied if the perceived performance exceeds it. If the apparent performance does not meet the client's expectations, the expectation is negatively confirmed, and the consumer is dissatisfied.

2.3. Behavioral intention

Behavioral intention is the motivating component of a volitional activity, according to the theory of reasoned action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), and it is significantly associated with the behavior itself (Jang and Namkung, 2009). Although there are still debates concerning the degree of association between behavioral intentions and actual conduct, it appears that behavioral intention is a decent predictor of future behavior (Taylor and Baker, 1994). Thus, restaurant practitioners can benefit from a better knowledge of the factors that influence pleasant post-dining behavioral intentions such as positive reviews, recommending the restaurant to others, loyalty, and repeat purchases.

2.4. Hypothesis Development

2.4.1. Influence of Service Quality Attributes on Satisfaction

The causal direction between service quality and customer satisfaction has shown varied results. Bitner (1990), for example, established a model for evaluating service encounters and empirically shown that pleasure was a predictor of service quality. Many other studies, on the other hand, have found that perceived service quality has an impact on customer satisfaction (Cronin & Taylor, 1992). Yoo et al. (2000) also looked at the causal relationship between service quality and satisfaction. The data revealed that satisfaction was a predictor of perceived service quality rather than the other way around. Taylor and Baker (1994) stated that service quality better explains customer satisfaction, and the coefficient of the path from service quality to customer satisfaction in the service sector is larger than the coefficient of the road from customer satisfaction to service quality. As a result, it is possible to speculate that:

H1: *In a Chinese restaurant, service quality qualities have a favorable impact on guests' satisfaction.*

2.4.2 Influence of Diner's Satisfaction on Post-Dining Behavioral Intentions

The literature on satisfaction and service quality supports satisfaction's significance in predicting behavioral intentions (Parasuraman et al., 1991; Zeithaml et al., 1996; Yu and Dean, 2001). Behavioral intents have been addressed in the form of good word-of-mouth communications, customer loyalty, and revisit intention for the purposes of this study. Dining satisfaction has a significant impact on post-dining behavioral intentions, according to Kivela et al. (1999). Customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions toward mid-to-upscale restaurants are linked, according to Namkung and Jang (2007). Customer satisfaction was also linked to return intention and favorable word-of-mouth recommendation in university foodservice dining operations, according to Kim and Moon (2009). All of these findings indicate the restaurant industry's significant relationship between dining pleasure and post-dining behavioral intention. As a result, the following hypothesis was suggested in this study:

H2: *The level of satisfaction among diners has a favorable impact on their post-dining behavioural intentions.*

2.5. Theoretical Underpinning and Research Framework

The Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) theory is used to underpin the theoretical framework in this investigation (Jacoby, 2002). Stimulus refers to factors that have the ability to influence an individual's internal states. Internal processes and structures that function as a mediator between stimuli and an individual's ultimate behaviors, reactions, or responses are referred to as the Organism. The result of an individual's actions, both deliberate and unintentional, is represented by their response (Abdullah et al., 2016; Abdullah et al., 2017). In this study, three aspects of service quality were chosen that are predicted to have a substantial beneficial impact on diners' pleasure (dependent variable). The level of satisfaction among diners is expected to have a beneficial impact on their post-dining behavioural intentions.

Figure: Conceptual Model showing the hypothesized relationship

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Development of Measures

To measure the constructs, the author created scales based on current research. All items were scored on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating severe disagreement and 5 indicating strong agreement. Five factors were used to assess meal quality: food presentation, healthiness, diversity, tastiness, and freshness (Sulek and Hensley, 2004; Namkung and Jang, 2007 and Jang and Namkung, 2009). Five criteria were used to evaluate employee service: (i) workers are courteous and helpful; (ii) employees have menu knowledge; (iii) service is timely; (iv) employees are attentive; and (v) service is dependable and consistent (Kivela et al., 1999; Brady and Cronin, 2001; Jang and Namkung, 2009). Internal design and décor, cleanliness, lighting and music, temperature, and personnel look were all used to gauge the atmosphere (Ryu and Jang, 2007, 2008; Jang and Namkung, 2009). To gauge customer satisfaction, three criteria were used: (i) this restaurant can better fulfill my expectations, (ii) I have no complaints about this restaurant, and (iii) I am extremely satisfied with the whole experience at this restaurant (Oliver, 1997; Ryu et al., 2008). Three questions were used to assess behavioral intentions: (i) I will continue to use this restaurant, (ii) I will recommend this restaurant to people who want my opinion, and (iii) I would like to return to this restaurant in the future (Zeithaml, 1988). The questionnaire was written in English.

3.2. Population of the study

In Bangladesh, there are several Chinese restaurants that serve Chinese food. All diners who have dined in a Chinese restaurant in Bangladesh are included in this study's population.

3.3. Sampling and Data Collection

According to Roscoe (1975), sample sizes for most studies should be greater than 30 but less than 500. In this study, the author created a structured questionnaire and used an online

survey to gather data from 212 respondents. To obtain data from the intended respondents, the author utilized a Google form. The questionnaire link was delivered via Facebook, email, WeChat, and other social media platforms. For the study, the author employed both judgemental and convenience sampling methods. The data was collected around between January and February of 2021.

3.4. Data Analysis

The data analysis was carried out utilizing for a thorough examination of the data. To test the hypothesis and determine the mean and standard deviation, step-wise regression was used to determine the link between the independent and dependent variables, as well as to measure the diner's pleasure and post-dining behavioral intention. In certain situations, Microsoft Excel was utilized to do computations. For descriptive and multiple regression analyses, the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 22 software was utilized.

4. Analysis and Presentation of Findings:

The overall sample description and descriptive statistics of each research concept are explained first in this section. The hypothesis test was then used to determine the connections between each of the study's variables. Finally, the data linked to the hypotheses involving perceived quality characteristics, diner satisfaction, and post-dining behavioral intention are summarized in this section.

4.1. Validity and Reliability issues:

Table 1: Reliability Statistics:

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.897	0.899	4

[Note: SPSS version 22 has been used to calculate the above tables]

Source: software output

The Alpha value is the most essential statistic in terms of dependability, according to the current study's validity and reliability test. Cronbach's Alpha is 0.897 in this situation, as shown in table: 1. Finally, given all of the scale reliability values surpassed 0.70, it can be inferred that all of the service quality attributes are internally consistent. The Alpha score is 0.897, according to Table 1 of the reliability statistics. The Alpha value of diner satisfaction was found to be higher than Nunnally and Bernstein's (1994) suggested criteria of 0.70 for scale dependability.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics for each study constructs:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Food Quality	212	1.00	7.00	5.5585	1.14642
Employee Service Quality	212	1.00	7.00	5.4274	1.23388
Atmospherics	212	1.00	7.00	5.1009	1.26947
Diner Satisfaction	212	1.00	7.00	5.2736	1.34301
Behavioral Intension	212	1.00	7.00	5.1415	1.37030
Valid N (listwise)	212				

Table:2 [Note: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences- SPSS (version. 22) has been used to calculate the Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum and Maximum value of each of the constructs]

Source: software output

Food quality varies from 1 to 7, with a mean of 5.5585 and a standard deviation of 1.14642 based on the 212 samples. The mean and standard deviation for employee service quality are 5.4274 and 1.23388, respectively. The mean and standard deviation for atmospherics are

5.1009 and 1.26947, respectively, with lowest and maximum values ranging from 1 to 7. Diner satisfaction ranges from 1 to 7, with the mean and standard deviation being 5.2736 and 1.34301, respectively. The mean and standard deviation of behavioral intention, which range from 1 to 7, are 5.1415 and 1.37030, respectively. In table 2, it can be seen that virtually all of the Means are comparable. A high standard deviation indicates that the data are spread out, implying that diners have a broad range of opinions, whereas a low standard deviation indicates that diners have similar opinions.

4.3. Hypotheses Test:

Table 3: Correlations

		Diner Satisfaction	Food Quality	Employee Service Quality	Atmospherics	Behavioral Intention
Diner Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	0.511(**)	0.660(**)	0.618(**)	0.792(**)
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	212	212	212	212	212
Food Quality	Pearson Correlation	0.511(**)	1	0.784(**)	0.762(**)	0.401(**)
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	212	212	212	212	212
Employee Service Quality	Pearson Correlation	0.660(**)	0.784(**)	1	0.811(**)	0.578(**)
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	212	212	212	212	212
Atmospherics	Pearson Correlation	0.618(**)	0.762(**)	0.811(**)	1	0.574(**)
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	212	212	212	212	212
Behavioral Intention	Pearson Correlation	0.792(**)	0.401(**)	0.578(**)	0.574(**)	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	212	212	212	212	212

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Table 3: [Note: SPSS version-22 has been used to calculate the above Table-3]

Source: software output

4.3.1. Pearson Correlation

A correlation coefficient is a handy method to express the relationship between two variables using a single number that ranges from -1 to 1. Morgan et al. (2004) defined the following terms: -1.0 (perfect negative correlation), 0.0 (no correlation), and +1.0 (perfect positive correlation) (a perfect positive correlation). Pallant (2001) proposed the following r-value interpretation. The strength of the link between two variables is shown by the r-value. $r = 0.10$ to 0.29 or -0.10 to -0.29 little, $r = 0.30$ to 0.49 or -0.30 to -0.49 medium, and $r = .50$ to 1.0 or -0.50 to -1.0 big. In the table 3 above, the Pearson correlation analysis was performed on the three interval scaled variables. The sample size is 212 people, with a significance level of 0.01 ($p < 0.01$).

Hypothesis # 1

“What are the major service quality factors impacting diner satisfaction in Chinese restaurants?” asks the first study question. The first hypothesis investigates the relationship

between service quality variables and diner satisfaction in Bangladesh's Chinese restaurant sector. The following is the hypothesis:

H1: In a Chinese restaurant, service quality qualities have a favorable impact on guests' satisfaction.

Table 3 shows that the correlations (r) of food quality, service quality, and physical environment are 0.511, 0.660, and 0.618, respectively, and that each determinant's p -value is 0.000, which is less than the significant threshold (0.01). As a result, the H1 hypothesis is accepted, and it is determined that each indicator of service quality qualities affects diner satisfaction in Chinese restaurant settings in Bangladesh positively (strongly).

Hypothesis # 2

The second hypothesis referred back to the second study question: What effect does diner pleasure have on post-dining behavioral intentions? The following is the hypothesis:

H2: The level of satisfaction among diners has a favorable impact on their post-dining behavioural intentions.

Table 3 shows that the correlation (r) of diner satisfaction is 0.792, with a p -value of 0.000.

As a result, the H2 hypothesis is accepted, and it can be inferred that diner pleasure has a substantial influence on post-dining behavioral intention in Bangladeshi Chinese restaurants.

4.3.2. Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.792(a)	0.628	0.626	0.83794

a Predictors: (Constant), Diner Satisfaction

** Significant at the level of 0.005

Note: SPSS version-22 has been used to calculate the above Table-4

Source: software output

The R value was 0.792, as shown in table 4. As a result, the R value (0.792) for diner satisfaction indicated that the independent variable (diner satisfaction) had a significant impact on the dependent variable (post-dining behavioral intention). It was also discovered that the coefficient of determination, or R-square value, was 0.628, indicating that the independent variables (diner satisfaction) of the Chinese restaurant in Bangladesh are responsible for 62 percent of the variation in the dependent variable (post-dining behavioral intention).

Table 5: Coefficients (a)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	B	Std. Error
1	(Constant)	0.878	0.234		3.757	0.000
	Diner Satisfaction	0.808	0.043	0.792	18.822	0.000

a Dependent Variable: Behavioral Intention

** Significant at the level of 0.005

Note: SPSS version-22 has been used to calculate the above Table-5]

Source: software output

When all other independent variables are maintained constant, unstandardized coefficients reveal how much the dependent variable (Behavioral Intention) fluctuates with the independent variable (diner satisfaction). The beta coefficients showed how and to what extent diner pleasure influences post-dining behavioral intention. Diner satisfaction ($\beta = 0.792$,

$t=18.822, p<0.001$) was shown to have the greatest positive effect on behavioral intention in the Chinese restaurant category in Bangladesh.

5. Conclusion and limitations

In order to understand comprehensive evaluation of restaurant experience in the context, this study proposed a conceptual model that explicitly accounts for the effects of three major elements of restaurant service quality (e.g. food, atmosphere, and employee service) on customer satisfaction, as well as the effect of satisfaction on behavioral intentions (e.g. positive word-of-mouth, revisit intention, and loyalty). The findings of this study revealed that three perceived foodservice quality attributes, such as food quality, employee service, and atmospheres, have a significant positive impact on Chinese restaurant customer satisfaction, as well as customer satisfaction has a positive impact on post-dining behavioral intention (word-of-mouth, loyalty, and revisit). For both academics and practitioners, the findings on the connections between service quality, customer satisfaction, and purchasing behavior have significant practical consequences. The findings of this study will give vital guidance to management in developing a plan to deliver improved customer service.

There are some flaws in this study as well. The study's conclusions are based on information gathered from customers who dined in a Chinese restaurant in Bangladesh. As a result, careful generalization of the findings is required. When applied to other sorts of restaurants, such as casual dining, upmarket fine dining, and so on, the findings should be taken with caution.

Reference

- Abdullah, D., Jayaraman, K., & Kamal, S. B. M. (2016). A conceptual model of interactive hotel website: The role of perceived website interactivity and customer perceived value toward website revisit intention. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37 (16), 170 –175. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)30109-5](http://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)30109-5).
- Abdullah, D., Jayaraman, K., Shariff, D. N., Bahari, K. A., & Nor, N. M. (2017). The effects of perceived interactivity, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness on online hotel booking intention: A conceptual framework. *International Academic Research Journal of Social Science*, 3 (1), 16–23. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)00079-4](http://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)00079-4).
- Anderson, R.E. (1973). Consumer dissatisfaction: the effect of disconfirmed expectancy on perceived product performance. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 10 (1), 38–44.
- Bitner, M. J. (1990). Evaluating service encounters: The effects of physical surroundings and employee responses. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(2), 69–82.
- Brady, M.K. and Cronin, J.J. (2001). Some new thoughts on conceptualizing perceived service quality: a hierarchical approach. *Journal of Marketing*, 65 (3), 34-49.
- Chow, I.H., Lau, V.P., Lo, T.W., Sha, Z., Yun, H. (2007). Service quality in restaurant operations in China: decision- and experiential-oriented perspectives. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 26 (3), 698–710.
- Cronin, J. J., & Taylor, S. A. (1992). Measuring service quality: Are-examination and extension. *Journal of Marketing*, 56(3), 55-68.
- Day, R. L. (1984). Modelling Choices Among Alternative Responses to Dissatisfaction. *Advances of Consumer Research*, 11(1), 496–499.
- Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*, Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA.
- Fitzsimmons J. A. and Fitzsimmons, M. J. (2008). *Service Management: Operations, Strategy, Information Technology*. 6th Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Howard, J.A., Sheth, J.N. (1969). *The Theory of Buyer Behavior*. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Jacoby, J. (2002). Stimulus-organism-response reconsidered: An evolutionary step in modeling (consumer) behavior. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 12 (1), 51-57. <http://doi.org/10.1207/153276602753338081>

- Jang, S. and Namkung, Y. (2009). Perceived quality, emotions, and behavioral intentions: application of an extended Mehrabian-Russell model to restaurants. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(4), 451-60.
- Kim, W.G., Moon, Y.J. (2009). Customers' cognitive, emotional, and actionable response to the servicescape: a test of the moderating effect of the restaurant type. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 28, 144-156.
- Kivela, J., Inbakaran, R., Reece, J. (1999a). Consumer research in the restaurant environment, part 1: a conceptual model of dining satisfaction and return patronage. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 11 (5), 205-222.
- Kivela, J., Reece, J., Inbakaran, R. (1999b). Consumer research in the restaurant environment, part 2: research design and analytical methods. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 11 (6), 269-286.
- Kivela, J., Inbakaran, R., Reece, J. (2000). Consumer research in the restaurant environment, part 3: analysis, findings and conclusions. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 12 (1), 13-30.
- Ladhari, R., Brun, I., Morales, M. (2008). Determinants of dining satisfaction and post dining behavioral intentions. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27 (4), 563-573.
- Mehrabian, A., & Russell, J.A. (Eds.). (1974). *An approach to environmental psychology*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Free Press.
- Namkung, Y., Jang, S. (2007). Does food quality really matter in restaurant? Its impact on customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 31 (3), 387-410.
- Namkung, Y., & Jang, S. (2008). Are highly satisfied restaurant customers really different? A quality perception perspective. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 20 (2), 142-155.
- Oliver, R.L. (1981). Measurement and evaluation of satisfaction process in retail setting. *Journal of Retailing*, 57, 25-48.
- Oliver, R.L., Swan, J.E. (1989). Equity and disconfirmation perceptions as influences on merchant and product satisfaction. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 16 (December), 372-383.
- Oliver, R.L. (1997). *Satisfaction: A Behavioral Perspective on the Consumer*. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., Berry, L.L. (1988). Servqual: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64 (Spring), 12-40.
- Roscoe, J. T. (1975). *Fundamental Research Statistics for the Behavioral Sciences* (2nd ed.). New York: Holt Rinehart & Winston.
- Ryu, K., Jang, S. (2007). The effect of environment perceptions on behavioral intentions through emotions: the case of upscale restaurants. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 31 (1), 56-72.
- Ryu, K., Han, H. and Kim, T.H. (2008). The relationships among overall quick-casual restaurant image, perceived value, customer satisfaction, and behavioral intentions. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 27(3), 459-69.
- Ryu, K., and Han, H. (2010). Influence of the Quality of Food, Service, and Physical Environment on Customer Satisfaction and Behavioral Intention in Quick-Casual Restaurants: Moderating Role of Perceived Price. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 34, 310-329.
- Stevens, P., Knutson, B. and Patton, M. (1995). DINESERV: A tool for measuring service quality in restaurants. *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration Quarterly*, 36 (2), 56-60.
- Sulek, J.M., Hensley, R.L. (2004). The relative importance of food, atmosphere, and fairness of wait: the case of a full-service restaurant. *Cornell Hotel and Restaurant Administration*, 45 (3), 235-247.
- Taylor, S. A., & Baker, T. L. (1994). An assessment of the relationship between services quality and customer satisfaction in the formation of consumers' purchase intentions. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(summer), 163-178.
- Westbrook, R.A., Reilly, M.D. (1983). Value-percept disparity: an alternative to the disconfirmation of expectations theory of consumer satisfaction. *Advances in Consumer Research* 10, 256-261.
- Yoo, B., Donthu, N. and Lee, S. (2000). An examination of selected marketing mix elements and brand equity. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 28 (2), 278-90.

- Yuksel, A., Yuksel, F. (2002). Measurement of tourist satisfaction with restaurant services: a segment-based approach. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 9 (1), 52-68.
- Zeithaml, V. A. (1988). Consumer perceptions of price, quality, and value: a means end model and synthesis of evidence. *Journal of Marketing*, 52(July), 2-22.
- Zeithaml, V. A., Berry, L. L., & Parasuraman, A. (1996). The behavioral consequences of service quality. *Journal of Marketing*, 60(2), 31-46.

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